

Post Graduate Research Contributions in Veterinary Sciences Theses: A study of Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology of Jammu during the period from 2006 to 2025

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: This study examines the research contributions reflected in Postgraduate (MVSc) theses submitted to the Faculty of Veterinary Sciences and Animal Husbandry at Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology of Jammu during the period from 2006 to March 2025. The objective is to analyze research productivity patterns and enhance the accessibility and visibility of institutional research output, in alignment with national priorities that emphasize inclusive, digitally enabled higher education systems.

Methodology: A descriptive and analytical research design was adopted. Data were collected from the Faculty Library at R.S. Pura Campus, departmental records, the KOHA-based library management system, and the KRISHIKOSH repository. Bibliographic data relating to 486 MVSc theses were compiled and analyzed using parameters such as year-wise research output, gender-wise authorship, division-wise distribution, and supervisory productivity. The data were organized and analyzed using spreadsheet-based tools.

Findings: The analysis revealed a total of 486 postgraduate theses, with male researchers contributing a higher proportion than female researchers. Research output peaked during selected years,

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indicating periodic growth trends. Veterinary Surgery and Radiology emerged as the most productive division, followed by Veterinary Public Health and Epidemiology and Animal Nutrition. Supervisory contributions were concentrated among a limited number of faculty members, reflecting subject-specific research strengths.

Implications: The findings provide valuable insights for collection development, research planning, and academic supervision in veterinary sciences. The study supports evidence-based decision-making for strengthening institutional repositories, promoting balanced research growth across disciplines, and enhancing the role of academic libraries in supporting national development goals.

Keywords: Faculty Library, KRISHIKOSH, PostGraduate, Research Contributions, Veterinary Surgery and Radiology, Research work

1. INTRODUCTION

Research is an essential part of every university. It enables the generation of intellectual property, discoveries, and innovations with values. Research productivity or contribution may often be considered a key role in achieving quality knowledge and disseminating knowledge worldwide (Sahu and Neelam, 2023). Veterinary research serves as the interface between science and animal and human health. In today's society, the public has high expectations for the protection of human and animal health and finding treatments for emerging and ongoing diseases. Because of these high expectations, there is an urgent need to provide adequate resources and training programs at veterinary institutions to facilitate veterinary research.

Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology of Jammu, popularly known as SKUAST-Jammu came into existence on 20th September 1999 following the amendment in Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology Act, 1982, through the State Legislature. The university is mandated to address the basic, strategic and applied research related to enhanced production in agriculture and allied sectors (livestock health improvement and quality-based products). (<https://www.skustjammu.ac.in>). SKUAST-Jammu is striving to achieve high standards of excellence in education, research and extension for the betterment of farming community of the region. The university comprises distinct faculties, including the Faculty of Agriculture, Faculty of Veterinary Sciences & Animal Husbandry, Faculty of Horticulture and Forestry, Faculty of Dairy Technology, Faculty of Agricultural Engineering, Faculty of Basic Sciences and the School of Biotechnology. SKUAST-J is a multi-campus university with its headquarter located at Chatha, Jammu. There are Eight Research Stations/Sub-Stations and nine KVKs in the University which are in different agro-climatic zones of Jammu region for catering the location-specific needs of the farming community. University pursues research of high standard through projects funded by various central and state agencies (Rani et al., 2024).

1.1. Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology of Jammu (SKUAST-Jammu) Library

Agricultural and Veterinary University libraries play a significant role in advancing research and development in their respective fields. Libraries offer well-catalogued materials, making it easier for researchers to locate and retrieve specific information efficiently. The Library of SKUAST-Jammu comprises of Central Library at Faculty of Agriculture (FOA), Main Campus, Chatha and Faculty Library at Faculty of Veterinary Sciences & Animal Husbandry (FVSc& AH), R.S. Pura Campus. Both the libraries have open access and are housed in their respective modern and spacious buildings and also contribute and support SKUAST-Jammu in building an internationally top ranked academic and research driven institution by establishing a knowledge hub. In both the libraries the collection comprises of documents in the field of Agricultural, Veterinary and allied sciences. In order to facilitate routine operations, the Faculty Library of the University is equipped with an Integrated Library Management System (LMS) – KOHA and is RFID equipped to facilitate the routine of e-resources, services. All these available in the Faculty Library digitized and have been uploaded to the KOHA Software with RFID tagged. The process of Technical Services which include accessioning, cataloguing, classification, processing, etc and RFID tagging of all 486 postgraduate theses available in the Faculty Library has been initiated and completed during the year 2024-2025 to streamline operations by enabling faster, easier, and more accurate security, and inventory management, ultimately improving efficiency and the users' experience. It facilitates to strengthen the:

- Enhanced security and theft prevention
- Improved Inventory management
- Reduced labor costs and increased productivity
- Cost-Effectiveness
- Data Collection and Analysis
- Integration with Other Systems

The Faculty Library has created various new facilities from the available existing resources in and around the library building for the library users including students, teachers and researchers for maximum usages of available library resources. Online Library system consisting of network terminals for providing access to e-journals, e-books, e-theses, internet and other e-reference resources are provided to the scientists, scholars, students and staff. Library functions and requirements have been kept in view while planning and equipping it. Library services are witnessing radical changes world over and accessibility and instant retrieval of information is the focus.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Research productivity has emerged as a significant measurement for assessing academic growth, institutional performance, and the advancement of knowledge across disciplines. Various studies have examined research productivity through bibliometric and Scientometric approaches, focusing on doctoral/postgraduate theses, institutional output, subject-wise distribution, and chronological growth patterns in agricultural and allied sciences.

Rani et al. (2024) conducted an analytical study on the research productivity of doctoral theses in veterinary sciences. Their findings revealed that the highest volume of research output was recorded in 2018, accounting for 19.14% of the total theses, followed closely by 2017 and 2019. The study further identified Parasitology as the most productive subject area, followed by Veterinary Physiology, Biochemistry, Veterinary Public Health, and Epidemiology. This study highlights subject concentration trends and underscores the growing emphasis on specialized veterinary disciplines.

Agrawal, Kumar, and Savary (2024) examined agricultural research in India using data sourced from the ICAR. Their analysis emphasized the role of ICAR in promoting purpose-driven research and highlighted its contribution to identifying long-term research patterns in Indian agriculture. The study concluded that agricultural research in India has evolved significantly over recent decades, adapting to emerging challenges such as food security, sustainability, and climate change.

Sahu and Neelam (2023) analyzed the publication trends and growth patterns of documents produced by Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya, Bilaspur, and Harishchandra Singh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar. Using bibliometric techniques and data indexed in the Web of Science database for the period 1991–2022, the study found that both universities demonstrated consistent research output across several parameters. The findings indicate balanced institutional growth and increasing research visibility at the national and international levels.

Sahu and Yadav (2023) investigated the research productivity in the subject of Agronomy. Their study revealed that maize was the most researched crop, followed by wheat and rice. This crop-wise analysis reflects national agricultural priorities and the importance of staple crops in research agendas aimed at enhancing food production and agronomic efficiency.

Adekunle and Madukoma (2022) explored the research productivity of doctoral students in universities in Ogun State. The study revealed that majority of respondents scored below average on key research productivity criteria. However, it also highlighted that doctoral students with higher levels of research self-efficacy demonstrated significantly better research output, establishing a positive relationship between self-efficacy and productivity.

Kadam and Bhusawar (2021) examined trends in research productivity and found fluctuations characterized by periods of growth and decline. Their study indicated that most research articles fell within broad subject categories, particularly in agricultural, biological, and botanical sciences, reflecting interdisciplinary research trends.

Garg and Bansal (2021) analyzed thesis production at Govind Ballabh Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pant Nagar, and Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana. Their findings revealed that a large number of female scholars were pursuing higher education in agricultural sciences and were awarded M.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees, indicating increasing gender participation in agricultural research.

Singh et al. (2020) conducted a historical analysis of horticulture theses in India from 1952 to 2017. The study revealed that Himachal Pradesh emerged as a leading contributor, with Dr. Y. S. Parmar University of Horticulture and Forestry producing the highest number of theses. This highlights regional specialization and institutional leadership in horticultural research.

The collective findings emphasize the need for continued investment in research infrastructure, capacity building, and supportive academic environments to enhance research output and quality.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study year-wise research contribution of Post Graduate theses at SKUAST - Jammu about Veterinary Sciences from 2006 to 31-03-2025.
- To identify the Gender-wise in Authorship pattern.
- To study Division-wise contribution of theses submitted by the Post Graduate theses at SKUAST - Jammu about Veterinary Sciences.
- To identify the Gender-wise in Guide ship/Chairmanship pattern.
- To study the research trend and subject areas in the subject of Veterinary Sciences at SKUAST – Jammu.

4. METHODOLOGY

In the present research paper, the last 19 years of the Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology, Jammu, **2006 to 31-03-2025**, Post Graduate (MVSc) evaluation has been done based on the theses. The data collection for this has been taken from Faculty Library, SKUAST-J, R.S.Pura, all the departments/divisions of Faculty of Veterinary Sciences and Animal Husbandry, LMS – Koha and ICAR Krishikosh. Mainly SKUAST – Jammu, Post Graduate (MVSc) theses cover subject like Veterinary Sciences and Animal Husbandry. This study deals with the methodology adopted in the analysis of the research contributions of SKUAST – Jammu through the Post Graduate (MVSc) theses submitted by the divisions/departments of Faculty of Veterinary Sciences and Animal Husbandry (18). The bibliographic data were entered into the MS Excel Spreadsheet. The data sheet contained information regarding the year in which the theses were submitted, Gender-wise distribution, Division-wise distribution, ranking of guides', the name of the supervisor/ research guide and the subject of the theses for the analysis.

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDING

5.1. Year-Wise Contribution of Post Graduate theses

Table-1 indicates the year-wise contribution of Post Graduate theses submitted by the research scholars in the SKUAST-J, Faculty Library, R.S.Pura:

Table-1 Year-wise Contribution of Post Graduate Theses of Veterinary Sciences

SI. No.	Year	No. of Thesis submitted	Cumulative Record	%
01	2006	01	01	0.21
02	2007	01	02	0.21
03	2008	07	09	1.44
04	2009	12	21	2.47
05	2010	21	42	4.32

SI. No.	Year	No. of Thesis submitted	Cumulative Record	%
06	2011	31	73	6.38
07	2012	44	117	9.05
08	2013	45	162	9.26
09	2014	37	199	7.61
10	2015	35	234	7.20
11	2016	41	275	8.44
12	2017	37	312	7.61
13	2018	30	342	6.17
14	2019	18	360	3.70
15	2020	07	367	1.44
16	2021	43	410	8.85
17	2022	37	447	7.61
18	2023	13	460	2.67
19	Up to 31-03-2025	26	486	5.35
	Total	486		100.00

Figure-1 Year-wise Contribution of Post Graduate Theses of Veterinary Sciences

Table 1 and Figure 1 show the number of theses submitted each year from 2006 to 31-03-2025 about Veterinary Sciences along with the cumulative total and the percentage, a total of 486 Post Graduate theses has been received in Faculty Library, R.S.Pura. The research output started very low, with only 1 thesis each year, contributing to just 0.21% per year. This indicates the initial stage of academic activity. Submissions rose from 7 in 2008 to 21 in 2010, showing growing research involvement. A significant rise is seen from 2011 to 2013. This period shows strong academic development, reaching around 9% contribution per year, which is among the highest. From 2014–2017, the number of theses remained consistently high i.e between 35 and 41 theses per year. Each year contributed around 7–8%, this suggests a stable and productive research environment. The sharp drop in 2020 (1.44%) may indicate external challenges. A strong recovery is observed in the year 2021 with 43 theses (8.85%), showing renewed research activity. Output declined again after 2022, especially in 2023.

2024 to 31-03-2025, a total of 26 theses has been submitted so far, contributing 5.35%, indicating moderate ongoing progress.

5.2. Gender-wise Contribution of Post Graduate theses

Table-2 indicates the Gender-wise contribution of PostGraduate Theses submitted by the research scholars in the SKUAST-J, Faculty Library, R.S.Pura:

Table-2 Gender-wise Contribution of Post Graduate Theses of Veterinary Sciences

SI. No.	Gender	No. of Authors	%
01	Male	323	66.46
02	Female	163	33.54
Total		486	100.00

Table-2 shows the gender-wise contribution of theses. The maximum number of contributions as authorship was male researchers i.e. 323 (66.46%) and number of female researchers were 163 (33.54 %).

5.3. Division-wise Contribution of Post GraduateTheses

Table-3 indicates the Division-wise contribution of theses submitted by the research scholars in their respective divisions/departments of SKUAST-J, libraries:

Table-3 Division-wise Contribution of Post GraduateTheses of Veterinary Sciences

S. No.	Division	No. of Theses submitted	%
01	Animal Genetics and Breeding	29	5.97
02	Animal Nutrition	48	9.88
03	Fisheries*	00	0.00
04	Livestock Farm Complex*	00	0.00
05	Livestock Production Management	25	5.14
06	Livestock Products Technology	37	7.61
07	Veterinary Anatomy	10	2.06
08	Veterinary Animal Husbandry Extension Education	28	5.76
09	Veterinary Clinical Complex	17	3.50
10	Veterinary Gynecology and Obstetrics	24	4.93
11	Veterinary Medicine	47	9.67
12	Veterinary Microbiology and Immunology	18	3.70
13	Veterinary Pharmacology and Toxicology	27	5.56
14	Veterinary Physiology and Biochemistry	21	4.32
15	Veterinary Parasitology	20	4.12
16	Veterinary Pathology	22	4.53
17	Veterinary Public Health and Epidemiology	51	10.49
18	Veterinary Surgery and Radiology	62	12.76
Total		486	100.00

*Non accreditation of Course by the Veterinary Council of India

Figure-3 Division-wise Contribution of Post Graduate Theses of Veterinary Sciences

It is clear from Table-3 and Figure-3 that maximum number of research work has been done in the subject/division of Veterinary Surgery and Radiology 62 (12.76%), followed by Veterinary Public Health and Epidemiology i.e.51 (10.49%) and in Animal Nutrition 48 (9.88%) of research work was done. Further, it has been observed that 47 (9.67%) research work has been done each in the division/subject of Veterinary Medicine, 37(7.61%) in the division of Livestock Products Technology, 29 (5.97%) in the division of Animal Genetics and Breeding, 28 (5.76%)in the divisions of Veterinary Animal Husbandry Extension Education,27 (5.56%) Veterinary Pharmacology and Toxicology, 25 (5.14%) in Livestock Production Management, 24 (4.93%) in the division of Veterinary Gynecology and Obstetrics, 21 (4.32%) in the divisions of Veterinary Physiology and Biochemistry, Veterinary Pathology 22 (4.53%), Veterinary Parasitology20 (4.12%) , 17 (3.50%) in the divisions of Veterinary Clinical Complex, 18 (3.70%) in the division of Veterinary Microbiology and Immunology and very less research work has been done in the subject/division of Veterinary Anatomy i.e. 10 (2.06%) and there was no research work done in the subject/division of Fisheries and Livestock Farm Complex. The main reason for this is that these divisions/departments have been established recently but the research work is ongoing.

5.4 Gender-wise Contributions of Guides/Supervisor in Post Graduate theses

Table-4 indicates the Gender-wise contributions of Post Graduate theses supervised by the research scholars of SKUAST-J:

Table-4 Gender-wise Contributions of Guides /Supervisor in Post Graduate Theses

SI. No.	Gender	No. of Supervisors	%
01	Male	72	80.68
02	Female	18	19.32
Total		90	100.00

Table-4 shows the gender-wise contribution of Guides/Supervisors. The maximum number of contributions as guideship was male supervisors i.e. 72 (80.68%) and number of female supervisors were 18 (19.32 %).

5.5 Research trend and subject areas of research contribution in Veterinary Sciences

Table-5 indicates the research trend and subject areas of research contribution of guides' supervised the research scholars in their respective subject/area of research.

There is a total of 90 guides who have supervised 486 research scholars, but only the top five ranked have been considered, while all others have been enclosed at the end in Appendice-1.

Table-5 Research trend and subject areas of research contribution in Veterinary Sciences

SI. No.	Name of the Guide	Division	Contributions/ No. of Student Guided	Rank
01	1. Dr.R.K.Sharma	Animal Nutrition	19	1
02	1. Dr. M.S. Bhadwal	Veterinary Surgery and Radiology	17	2
	2. Dr. Arvind Kumar	Livestock Products Technology	17	
03	1. Dr. S.K.Kotwal	Veterinary Public Health and Epidemiology	12	3
	2. Dr. Pranav Kumar	Veterinary Animal Husbandry Extension Education	12	
	3. Dr.H.R.Bhardwaj	Veterinary Surgery and Radiology	12	
	4. Dr. Ankur Rastogi	Animal Nutrition	12	
	5. Dr. Mohd. Rashid	Veterinary Public Health and Epidemiology	12	
04	1. Dr. Rajiv Singh	Veterinary Medicine	11	4
05	1. Dr. Rajesh Katoch	Veterinary Parasitology	10	5
	2. Dr. Rajinder Raina	Veterinary Pharmacology and Toxicology	10	
	3. Dr. A.K.Gupta	Veterinary Surgery and Radiology	10	
	4. Dr. R.B. Kushwaha	Veterinary Surgery and Radiology	10	

Table-5 and Figure-5 reflects a strong and consistent research trend in core and applied areas of veterinary sciences, with a notable emphasis on Animal Nutrition, Veterinary Surgery and Radiology, and Veterinary Public Health and Epidemiology. The highest number of research scholars guided is seen in Animal Nutrition, indicating it as the most dominant and emerging research trend, focusing on livestock productivity, feed efficiency, and nutritional management. Closely following is Veterinary Surgery and Radiology, highlighting increasing research interest in advanced diagnostic techniques, surgical interventions, and clinical innovations. Another significant trend is observed in Veterinary Public Health, Epidemiology, and Extension Education, reflecting a growing concern for zoonotic diseases, public health safety, disease surveillance, and farmer-oriented outreach programmes. Moderate but steady research engagement in Veterinary Medicine, Parasitology, Pharmacology, Toxicology, and Livestock Products Technology suggests a balanced research ecosystem addressing both preventive and curative aspects of animal health along with value addition and food safety.

Figure-5 Research trend and subject areas of research contribution in Veterinary Sciences

The major subject areas of research emerging from the table include Animal Nutrition, Veterinary Surgery and Radiology, Veterinary Public Health and Epidemiology, Veterinary Medicine, Veterinary Parasitology, Veterinary Pharmacology and Toxicology, Animal Husbandry Extension Education, and Livestock Products Technology. These subject areas collectively cover fundamental, clinical, and applied dimensions of veterinary science. The distribution of research scholars across these disciplines indicates an integrated approach towards improving animal health, enhancing livestock production, ensuring food safety, and addressing public health challenges. Overall, the table highlights a diverse yet application-oriented research focus, aligned with contemporary needs of the livestock and veterinary sector.

6. CONCLUSION

The study presents a comprehensive overview of research output in Veterinary Sciences from 2006 to March 2025, highlighting trends in productivity, gender participation, supervisory contribution, and subject-wise distribution. The keyword analysis of the Postgraduate theses shows that most research is focused on **clinical, diagnostic, and public health areas**, especially Veterinary Surgery and Radiology and Veterinary Public Health. Some areas like animal nutrition and pharmacology are also growing. However, some fields are still less explored and need more attention in the future. The research shows a strong focus on practical and useful topics, with gradual growth in different areas. The findings reveal significant growth in research activities, with Veterinary Surgery and Radiology emerging as the most productive area. Overall, the analysis provides valuable insights into the development and direction of veterinary research in the whole world and India and contributing to the mission of a developed Nation as Viksit Bharat @ 2047 envisions higher education libraries as dynamic, digitally advanced, and culturally rooted, inclusive and collaborative institutions.

7. SUGGESTIONS

- Efforts should be made to encourage greater participation of female researchers and supervisors in veterinary research.
- Balanced research development across less-represented subject areas should be promoted.
- Institutions may strengthen research support systems to enhance quality, collaboration and innovation in veterinary sciences.

8. FURTHER RESEARCH AREAS

- Comparative studies of veterinary research output across different universities or regions.
- Impact and assessment of veterinary research on animal health, public health and rural development.
- Bibliometric analysis of publications, citations, and collaboration patterns in veterinary sciences.

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APPENDIX

Sl. No.	Name of the Supervisor	No. of Student Supervised
01	Dr.R.K.Sharma	19
02	Dr. M.S.Bhadwal	17
03	Dr. Arvind Kumar	17
04	Dr. S.K.Kotwal	12
05	Dr. Pranav Kumar	12
06	Dr.H.R.Bhardwaj	12
07	DrAnkurRastogi	12
08	Dr. Mohd. Rashid	12
09	Dr. Rajiv Singh	11
10	Dr. Rajesh Katoch	10
11	Dr. A.K.Gupta	10
12	Dr. RajinderRaina	10
13	Dr. R.B.Kushwaha	10
14	Dr.S.K.Gupta	09
15	Dr.J.S.Soodan	09
16	Dr. Sunil Kumar	09
17	Dr. M.A.Malik	09
18	Dr. KafilHussain	09
19	Dr. Asma Khan	09
20	Dr. Nishant Kumar	09
21	Dr. A.K. Pathak	09
22	Dr. Z.F.Bhat	08
23	Dr. H.K. Sharma	08
24	Dr. M.A.Bhat	08
25	Dr. Rajesh Agrawal	08
26	Dr. ShaguftaAzmi	08
27	Dr.Utsav Sharma	07
28	Dr. Mudasir Sultana	06
29	Dr.V.S.Wazir	06
30	Dr. Ashok Kumar	06
31	Dr. DipanjaliKonwar	06
32	Dr. Jonali Devi	06
33	Dr. S.A.Khandi	06
34	Dr. ShafiqurRahman	06
35	Dr. AbhaTikoo	06
36	Dr. ShaliniSuri	05
37	Dr. A.K.Taku	05
38	Dr. AnishYadav	05
39	Dr. Kamal Sharma	05
40	Dr. Nrip Kishore Pankaj	05
41	Dr. Rajesh Godara	05
42	Dr. Nazam Khan	05
43	Dr. Neelesh Sharma	05
44	Dr. Rajinder Kumar Bhardwaj	05
45	Dr. PratikshaRaghuwanshi	04
46	Dr.WaquarA.A.Razzaque	04

SI. No.	Name of the Supervisor	No. of Student Supervised
47	Dr. JafrinAra Ahmed	04
48	Dr. M.M.S.Zama	04
49	Dr. Maninder Singh	04
50	Dr. Dharendra Kumar	04
51	Dr. Biswajit Brahma	04
52	Dr. Vikas Mahajan	04
53	Dr. R.K.Taggar	04
54	Dr. Nawab Nashiruddullah	04
55	Dr.S.R.Upadhyay	04
56	Dr. Sahar Masud	03
57	Dr. Pawan Kumar Verma	03
58	Dr. Shilpa Sood	03
59	Dr. Dibyendu Chakraborty	03
60	Dr. VikasPathak	03
61	Dr. ShahidPrawez	03
62	Dr. Sanjay Agarwal	03
63	Dr. D.K.Dwivedi	03
64	Dr.A.K.Das	03
65	Dr. Pankaj Gupta	03
66	Dr. Kawardeep Kour	03
67	Dr. Nishi Pande	02
68	Dr. P.S.Mahapatra	02
69	Dr. Gautam	02
70	Dr. Sudershan Kumar	02
71	Dr. Anil Kumar Pandey	02
72	Dr. Aditi Lal Koul	02
73	Dr. Suraj Amrutkar	02
74	Dr. Ankur Sharma	02
75	Dr. Sharad Kumar	02
76	Dr. Bharat Bhushan	01
77	Dr. Deepak Sharma	01
78	Dr. Yashwant Singh	01
79	Dr. K. Barman	01
80	Dr. Ravinder Kumar	01
81	Dr. N.K.Singh	01
82	Dr. Bablu Kumar	01
83	Dr. Pradeep Sawant	01
84	Dr. Bikram Singh	01
85	Dr. SankuBorkataki	01
86	Dr. Vijay Kumar Sharma	01
87	Dr. Sudhir Kumar	01
88	Dr. M.Mutha Rao	01
89	Dr. Pankaj Goswami	01
90	Dr. Sabahat Gazal	01
Total		486